

Code Summary

Qualitative Analysis BOR project

02/12/2024 11:25

File Type	Number of Files	Number of Coding References	Number of Words Coded	Number of Paragraphs Coded	Duration Coded
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Code

Codes\\Accountability

Nickname:

Classification:

Aggregated: No

Document	6	21	384	29
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Codes\\AI

Nickname:

Classification:

Aggregated: No

Document	7	89	1,983	105
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Codes\\Assessment

Nickname:

Classification:

Aggregated: No

Document	5	28	657	43
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Codes\\Bias (data, model...)

Nickname:

Classification:

Aggregated: No

Document	4	23	594	31
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File Type	Number of Files	Number of Coding References	Number of Words Coded	Number of Paragraphs Coded	Duration Coded
Codes\\Collaboration					
Nickname:					
Classification:					
Aggregated:	No				
Document	9	37	877	47	

Codes\\Data					
Nickname:					
Classification:					
Aggregated:	Yes				
Document	8	179	4,681	226	

Codes\\Data\Data challenges					
Nickname:					
Classification:					
Aggregated:	No				
Document	7	91	2,663	107	

Codes\\Data\Data integrity					
Nickname:					
Classification:					
Aggregated:	No				
Document	7	18	334	23	

Codes\\Data\Data quality					
Nickname:					
Classification:					
Aggregated:	No				
Document	8	50	1,340	75	

File Type	Number of Files	Number of Coding References	Number of Words Coded	Number of Paragraphs Coded	Duration Coded
Codes\\Data\Sensitive personal data					
Nickname:					
Classification:					
Aggregated: No					
Document	6	18	324	18	

Codes\\EDI - Equality, Diveristy and Inclusion

Nickname:

Classification:

Aggregated: No

Document	8	28	972	44	
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Codes\\Ethics

Nickname:

Classification:

Aggregated: No

Document	1	7	181	7	
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Codes\\Excellence

Nickname:

Classification:

Aggregated: No

Document	2	30	570	51	
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Codes\\Expectations

Nickname:

Classification:

Aggregated: Yes

Document	5	94	1,029	103	
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File Type	Number of Files	Number of Coding References	Number of Words Coded	Number of Paragraphs Coded	Duration Coded
Codes\\Expectations\\Expectations met					
Nickname:					
Classification:					
Aggregated: No					
Document	1	38	88	38	

Codes\\Expectations\\Information security

Nickname:

Classification:

Aggregated: No

Document	3	7	172	12	
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Codes\\Expectations\\Metrics

Nickname:

Classification:

Aggregated: No

Document	2	4	169	4	
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Codes\\Expectations\\Morality

Nickname:

Classification:

Aggregated: No

Document	1	1	1	1	
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Codes\\Expectations\\More focused sessions or discussion

Nickname:

Classification:

Aggregated: No

Document	1	9	100	9	
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File Type	Number of Files	Number of Coding References	Number of Words Coded	Number of Paragraphs Coded	Duration Coded
Codes\\Expectations\Patient and Public involvement					
Nickname:					
Classification:					
Aggregated: No					
Document	4	19	323	23	

Codes\\Expectations\Solutions					
Nickname:					
Classification:					
Aggregated: No					
Document	1	13	122	13	

Codes\\Expectations\What is already in place					
Nickname:					
Classification:					
Aggregated: No					
Document	1	3	54	3	

Codes\\FAIR principles					
Nickname:					
Classification:					
Aggregated: Yes					
Document	6	42	904	63	

Codes\\FAIR principles\Accessibility					
Nickname:					
Classification:					
Aggregated: No					
Document	6	16	347	24	

File Type	Number of Files	Number of Coding References	Number of Words Coded	Number of Paragraphs Coded	Duration Coded
Codes\\FAIR principles\Findability					
Nickname:					
Classification:					
Aggregated: No					
Document	1	2	37	5	

Codes\\FAIR principles\Interoperability					
Nickname:					
Classification:					
Aggregated: No					
Document	3	12	260	19	

Codes\\FAIR principles\Reusability					
Nickname:					
Classification:					
Aggregated: No					
Document	5	12	260	15	

Codes\\Open Research					
Nickname:					
Classification:					
Aggregated: Yes					
Document	8	144	3,044	180	

Codes\\Open Research\Obstacles to Open Research					
Nickname:					
Classification:					
Aggregated: No					
Document	6	60	1,280	81	

File Type	Number of Files	Number of Coding References	Number of Words Coded	Number of Paragraphs Coded	Duration Coded
Codes\\Open Research\Openness					
Nickname:					
Classification:					
Aggregated: Yes					
Document	7	60	1,328	70	

Codes\\Open Research\Openness\Open access

Nickname:

Classification:

Aggregated: No

Document	3	9	190	15	
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Codes\\Open Research\Openness\Open code

Nickname:

Classification:

Aggregated: No

Document	3	14	383	14	
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Codes\\Open Research\Openness\Open data

Nickname:

Classification:

Aggregated: No

Document	5	34	724	38	
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Codes\\Peer-review

Nickname:

Classification:

Aggregated: No

Document	7	26	574	28	
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File Type	Number of Files	Number of Coding References	Number of Words Coded	Number of Paragraphs Coded	Duration Coded
Codes\\Practical recommendations					
Nickname:					
Classification:					
Aggregated: Yes					
Document	10	255	5,484	358	

Codes\\Practical recommendations\\Awareness of what is going on**Nickname:****Classification:****Aggregated: No**

Document	2	11	170	15	
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Codes\\Practical recommendations\\Beyond Imperial**Nickname:****Classification:****Aggregated: No**

Document	1	4	33	4	
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Codes\\Practical recommendations\\Develop policies**Nickname:****Classification:****Aggregated: No**

Document	5	36	779	46	
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Codes\\Practical recommendations\\Enhance practices**Nickname:****Classification:****Aggregated: No**

Document	3	21	504	30	
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File Type	Number of Files	Number of Coding References	Number of Words Coded	Number of Paragraphs Coded	Duration Coded
Codes\\Practical recommendations\\Incentives and recognition					
Nickname:					
Classification:					
Aggregated:	No				
Document	5	37	1,051	74	

Codes\\Practical recommendations\\Public involvement					
Nickname:					
Classification:					
Aggregated:	No				
Document	9	49	1,351	90	

Codes\\Practical recommendations\\Standards					
Nickname:					
Classification:					
Aggregated:	No				
Document	4	20	431	20	

Codes\\Practical recommendations\\Take action from general to specific					
Nickname:					
Classification:					
Aggregated:	No				
Document	1	26	360	26	

Codes\\Practices and behaviours to improve research quality					
Nickname:					
Classification:					
Aggregated:	No				
Document	9	93	2,423	134	

File Type	Number of Files	Number of Coding References	Number of Words Coded	Number of Paragraphs Coded	Duration Coded
Codes\\Reliability					
Nickname:					
Classification:					
Aggregated: No					
Document	5	29	632	40	

Codes\\Research culture					
Nickname:					
Classification:					
Aggregated: No					
Document	6	44	1,300	80	

Codes\\Sustainability					
Nickname:					
Classification:					
Aggregated: No					
Document	8	28	641	29	

Codes\\Transparency					
Nickname:					
Classification:					
Aggregated: No					
Document	8	53	1,582	67	

Codes\\Trustworthiness					
Nickname:					
Classification:					
Aggregated: No					
Document	6	46	1,115	50	